

Project Management

Daniel Paul O'Donnell

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Types of DH from Øyvind's lecture

Ramsay's two categories

1. Makers/builders
2. Studies in Digital Culture

Burghart's three categories

1. Laboratores
2. Bellatores
3. Oratores

Different kinds of DH projects

- Projects that produce an end product:
 - Produce an edition
 - Write an article or book
- Projects that produce and maintain infrastructure
 - Build a resource (e.g. Corpus of Nigerian political discourse; corpus of syllabi, Dictionary)
 - Develop and maintain a standard (computer language, documentation)
 - Run a journal or annual summer school
- Project that build communities/foster collaboration
 - Communities of practice
 - National societies

Projects can be more than one of these

Difference between DH and H projects

- Traditionally, Humanities projects have been single-scholar
 - Motivation, focus, “leadership” has all been internal
 - You get your articles written (or you don’t)
 - You organise your time (or you don’t)
 - You keep yourself motivated (or you don’t)
- Digital Humanities projects involve multiple people (usually)
 - Somebody has to propose and develop idea, gather resources, lead work and people
 - People depend on each other to get things done
 - Project has to be interesting to all involved

Different kinds of projects need different kinds of resources and different kinds of leadership

- Projects with an end:
 - Keep people and resources focussed on outcome
 - One-off funding, volunteer labour is easier to use
- Infrastructure projects:
 - Keep people and resources focussed on the long haul
 - Continuous need for resources, more difficult to keep volunteers
- Community projects:
 - Create space for others to work
 - Often need very little funding or effort beyond maintaining excitement

Different kinds of leadership styles/structures

- Hierarchical
 - There is a “boss” who makes sure people get things done: holds people responsible, assigns tasks, checks work
- Inspirational
 - There is a “visionary” who excites others to work
 - Relies on enthusiasm and self-interest to get things done
 - Individual actors “follow their bliss”
- Community
 - There is a “chair” who makes sure the formal channels for decision making work
 - Group decides on direction and holds each other accountable

These styles work better for different people/projects

- I'm not good at the “boss” kind of leadership
 - I don't like/have no time for dealing with people who don't want to work, need instruction, and so on.
 - Like to establish goals and then let people use their own enthusiasm to get stuff done
 - Causes trouble in the project-with-and-end and (to a lesser extent) infrastructure projects
 - My projects can get bogged down
- I do better in the “visionary” and “chair” approaches
 - Have no trouble getting people excited about their own research

These styles work better for different people/projects

- I'm sure you can learn to improve your ability in weaker styles
- But on the whole, I think you should probably try to match your projects to your strengths
 - If your good at being a boss, you should structure your projects that way
 - If you are good at bridging/mediating, then you should build your projects that way
 - If you are good at establishing vision, you should focus on that as your contribution

My experience

Projects with an end

- Caedmon's Hymn
- Articles
- Visionary Cross project
- Future Commons?

Infrastructure Projects

- Text Encoding Initiative (TEI)
- Lethbridge journal incubator
- Digital Studies/Le champ numérique (journal)
- Digital Medievalist Journal
- Force11 Scholarly Communications Institute
- Future Commons?

Communities

- Digital Medievalist
- Global Outlook::Digital Humanities
- Canadian Society for Digital Humanities
- Force11
- Lethbridge Centre for the Study of Scholarly Communication

What about your experiences?

